

NAME: Michael Rießler
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LG: 188 Khalkha
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1. Segmental properties

contrast betw /n/ and /ng/ is synchronical only possible in syllable final-position,
(while contrast betw /g/ and /gh/ is also attested in medial syllable-initial (prevocalic) position) (p.157)

maximal syllable structure is CVVCCC (vowel kernel may be preceded by at most one C and followed by a cluster of up to three C)

the V can be short, long or a diphthong
in non-initial syllables, V can also be a non-phonemic schwa

onsetless syllables only word-initially

whether a C-combination can form a syllable coda or not depends on the phonetic properties of the C

permitted types of coda:

voiced+voiceless C, /daws/ [taws] 'salt', /alt/ [alʒ^ht] 'gold', /

bügd/ [pugt] 'all'

nasal+stop or affricate, /xünd/ [xunt] 'heavy', /möngg/

[moŋg] 'silver', /myanggh/ [m^jaŋg] 'thousand'

fricative+stop or affricate, /tsast/ [ts^has^ht] 'snowy'

three-C codas consist of a voiced C + fricative + stop or

affricate, /ilst/ [ilʒsʰt] 'sandy'

requirement on monosyllabic words: must have a heavy syllable rhyme, i.e. either a coda C, /xüŋg/ [xuŋ] 'person', a long V or a Diphthong, /düü/ [tuu] 'younger brother', /tsai/ [tsʰai] 'tea', or both, /tsaas/ [tsʰa:s] 'paper'
no (C)V-words with a short V

"A few monosyllabic **function words** are spelled and (transliterated) with a short vowel only [...] but they are pronounced (and may be phonemized) with a long vowel **in citation form** [...]" (s.158) [MR:that means that this monosyllabics have a long vowel only in citation form, but not when in use as a grammatical marker? thus they are not PW, maybe]

there are many bisyllabic and polysyllabic roots

reasons to question the traditional analysis of V quantity in non-initial syllables: possibly there is no short-long distinction of V in non-initial syllables (which is against the traditional view) and the 'short' V of non-initial syllables are in fact reduced (centralized) versions of the V of the preceding syllable (p.158)

Svantesson's rule for the quality of the reduced V in non-initial syllable: [MR: vowel harmony] (in Cyrillic orthography:) *xawar* [xawər] 'spring', *mongol* [mɔŋgɔlʒ] 'Mongol', *guril* [ɠʊrʲɪlʒ] ([i]-like quality of the reduced V after palatalized V in preceding syllable) (p.159)

Svantesson's rule for the place of reduced V in non-initial syllable: the schwa-vowels are inserted to make well-

formed syllables:

ard /ard/ [art] 'people', *bügd* /bügð/ [pugt] 'all', *uls* /uls/ [ʊlʒs] 'state' - no schwa, because clusters /rd gd ls/ (=voiced+voiceless C) can form a coda

xamar /xamr/ [xamər], 'nose', *xyatad* /xyatd/ [xja^htət] 'Chinese', *baatar* /baatr/ [pa:^htər] 'hero' - schwa, because clusters /mr td tr/ cannot form a coda at the surface (p.159)

in the case of three underlying final C, schwa inserted as far to the left as possible

a few cases, where the schwa insertion rule takes morphology into consideration, e.g. futuritive participle *xalax* [xalʒəx] 'to change' [MR: my gloss: xal-x change-part. fut.] vs. *xalx* [xalʒx] 'shield; Khalkha' (p.159)

Vowel harmony:

original back V vs. original front V, but synchronically pharyngeal harmony (V of the non-pharyngeal and the pharyngeal class cannot co-occur in the same word)

exception /i/, which can follow both classes of V

additionally labial harmony (concerns /a e o ö/

both V harmonies apply in roots, and in derived and inflected words

four archiphonemic entities: /A Ai U i/

exceptions of V harmony in a few elements (clitics):

possessive suffixes and negation particle /=güi/ (p.159f.)

// Prosodic properties

stress is not contrastive in words with more than one syllable

"...no agreement in the literature about the place of stress, or even if there is stress. The possible interaction of stress and intonation also remains to be investigated further."
(p.158)

III. Morpho-Syntax

agglutinative morphology

stems usually unchanged in the morphology, but a few other morphophonological processes connected with the V:

a) phonetic alternation between a schwa and Ø within the stem, *xamar* /xamr/ [xamər], 'nose' : abl. *xamraas* /xamras/

b) phonetic alternation between a schwa and Ø at the junction of stem and suffix, *xot* /xot/ 'town' : dat. *xotod* /xotd/

c) phonetic alternation between a schwa and Ø within the suffix, part.fut. *yawax* /yaw-°x/ 'to go' : instr. *yawaxaar* /yaw-x-ar/

c) connective C /g gh/ added between stem ending in a V and suffix beginning with a V (following pharyngeal harmony: /g/ after non-pharyngeal stems, /gh/ after pharyngeal stems, *xüü* /xüü/ 'boy' : instr. *xüügeer* /xüü/g-er/, *sanaa* /sana/ 'thought' : instr. *sanaagaar* /sana/gh-ar/)
(p.161)

IV Other